

Supplementary Information
for
‘Benchmark and application of unsupervised classification approaches for univariate data’

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Supplementary Method 1: Dataset generation

We generated 900 datasets, each consisting of 2000 breaking traces with known labels, with a varying number of clusters between 2 and 10 (100x 2 clusters ... 100x 10 clusters). To account for possibly large variations in cluster population which may occur experimentally, the distribution of clusters is logarithmically distributed with the most probable cluster having 10 times more traces than the least occurring one. For example, for 2 clusters the distribution is 9.09% and 90.91%, for 3 clusters 6.10%, 33.35% and 60.55%, etc.... The classes of the datasets were generated from an experimental dataset consisting of conductance vs. distance curves recorded on the OPE3 molecule¹. This is in contrast to previous studies where the data was purely synthetic^{2,3}.

The generation process is illustrated in Sup. Fig. 1. For each dataset, a defined number of single breaking traces were randomly selected from the experimental dataset (first panel of a). These selected traces (second panel) serve as the starting point for the different classes. Each cluster is built by generating additional traces via the addition of fluctuations to both the conductance values, as well as the displacement values of the starting trace (third panel). For the dataset shown

Supplementary Figure 1. Illustration of the generation of a dataset (1 of the 900) used for benchmarking consisting of 3 cluster. a) Generation of synthetic traces based on single experimental traces. b) Assembly of synthetic dataset consisting of 2000 traces based on individually generated breaking traces.

in Figure 2 of the main text, \log_{10} distributed Gaussian noise (mean 0, std: 1/3 order of magnitude) was added to the conductance. For the displacement, we note that the experimental data was acquired at a constant piezo speed and acquisition rate, resulting in a uniform separation Δd between the data points. To add local fluctuations to the displacement axis, uniform noise scaling between $-0.5 \cdot \Delta d$ and $0.5 \cdot \Delta d$ was added to each displacement value. On top of that, each trace was stretched with a uniformly distributed amount ranging between 0.75 and 1.5. Finally, the traces were then smoothed using a 5-point simple moving average and interpolated to ensure all traces have the same number of points per nanometer (fourth panel). We note that the traces have not been realigned after to addition of noise.

An example of a generated dataset with 3 clusters is illustrated in Sup. Fig. 1b, where the 2D conductance-displacement histogram of the three classes are plotted in the first three panels. The last panel presents the merged generated dataset consisting of 2000 traces. The plots also show the corresponding 1D conductance histogram.

Supplementary Figure 2 presents the source traces used for the generation of traces for the first twelve datasets containing 3 classes. In some datasets, the randomly picked source traces are quite distinct (for example 101 and 109), while in other cases they can be very similar (for example 104). This degree of similarity of the source traces influences the clustering accuracy. To show

this quantitatively, for each dataset we display the average FM index values obtained from the 28 feature space and 16 clustering algorithms, along side the FM index calculated for 28×28 + UMAP(cos.) + GAL, one of the best performing approaches. In the majority of cases, 28×28 + UMAP(cos.) + GAL is exceeding the average FM index and yields very high accuracies, with an FM index of 0.96 or higher for 11 of the 12 datasets. Only in simulation 104 where the traces are

Supplementary Figure 2. Generation of the datasets used for benchmarking.

The figure illustrates the generation process for a dataset (1 of the 900) consisting of 3 cluster.

very similar, the FM index is low.

Supplementary Method 2: Feature spaces

- **Lemmer:** As described in the publication by Lemmer et al.². As reference vector for the MCBJ benchmark, we use a tunneling trace following roughly the tunneling traces, obeying the equation $G = G_0 \cdot 10^{-3.3-7 \cdot d}$, with d the electrode separation.
- **Lemmer mod.:** As described in the publication by Lemmer et al.², but with the Hamming distance replaced by the length of the trace in nanometers. As reference vector for the MCBJ benchmark, we use a tunneling trace following roughly the tunneling traces, obeying the equation $G = G_0 \cdot 10^{-3.3-7 \cdot d}$, with d the electrode separation.
- **28×28:** Image of 28×28 pixels constructed as described in the publication by Cabosart et al.⁴ The x-limits were set from 0 to 2 nm and the y-limits from $10^{-6} G_0$ to $10 G_0$, binned on logarithmic scale.
- **Raw:** The raw data is treated as a vector in which each datapoint presents another dimension. The total number of dimensions is determined by the number of datapoints in the longest trace. For all shorter traces, zeros are added to ensure all traces have the same number of dimensions.
- **AE:** Dimensionality reduction using an autoencoder, as implemented in the Matlab Toolbox for Dimensionality Reduction by van der Maaten⁵. Available at <https://lvdmaaten.github.io/drtoolbox/>. Has been applied to the 28×28 and Raw feature space.
- **SNE:** Dimensionality reduction using stochastic neighbour embedding, as implemented in the Matlab Toolbox for Dimensionality Reduction by van der Maaten⁵. Available at <https://lvdmaaten.github.io/drtoolbox/>. Has been applied to the 28×28 and Raw feature space.
- **PCA:** Dimensionality reduction using principal component analysis, as implemented in the Matlab Toolbox for Dimensionality Reduction by van der Maaten⁵. Available at <https://lvdmaaten.github.io/drtoolbox/>. Has been applied to the 28×28 and Raw feature space.

- **k-PCA**: Dimensionality reduction using kernel-PCA autoencoder, as implemented in the Matlab Toolbox for Dimensionality Reduction by van der Maaten⁵. Available at <https://lvdmaaten.github.io/drtoolbox/>. Has been applied to the 28×28 and Raw feature space.
- **t-SNE**: Dimensionality reduction using an t-distributed SNE⁶. Build-in Matlab function, used with the default parameters. Has been applied to the 28×28 and Raw feature space using the euclidean, cosine, and Chebychev distance measure.
- **UMAP**: Dimensionality reduction using uniform manifold approximation and projection⁷, as implemented by Stephen Meehan. Available at <https://ch.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/71902-uniform-manifold-approximation-and-projection-umap>. Has been applied to the 28×28 and Raw feature space using the euclidean, cosine, and Chebychev distance measure.
- **Sammon**: Dimensionality reduction using Sammon mapping, as implemented in the Matlab Toolbox for Dimensionality Reduction by van der Maaten⁵. Available at <https://lvdmaaten.github.io/drtoolbox/>. Has been applied to the 28×28 and Raw feature space.
- **MDS**: Dimensionality reduction using multi-dimensional scaling, as implemented in the Matlab Toolbox for Dimensionality Reduction by van der Maaten⁵. Available at <https://lvdmaaten.github.io/drtoolbox/>. Has been applied to the 28×28 and Raw feature space.

For all algorithms, the default parameters have been employed, unless otherwise specified.

Supplementary Method 3: Clustering algorithms

- **k-means**: Matlab internal function
- **k-medoids**: Matlab internal function
- **FCM**: Clustering toolbox. Author: Janos Abonyi. <https://ch.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/7486-clustering-toolbox>

- **GK** Clustering toolbox. Author: Janos Abonyi. <https://ch.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/7486-clustering-toolbox>
- **SOM**: Matlab Neural Network Toolbox Network layout 1 x NoC.
- **Hierarchical**: Matlab internal function, with various distance metrics : median, centroid, average, weighted, Ward.
- **Shi & Malik**: Spectral clustering. Author: Ingo Bürk. https://github.com/areslp/matlab/tree/master/spectual_clustering. Options: k-Nearest neighbors
- **Jordan & Weiss**: Spectral clustering. Author: Ingo Bürk. https://github.com/areslp/matlab/tree/master/spectual_clustering. Options: k-Nearest neighbors
- **OPTICS**: OPTICS clustering. Author: Alex Kendall. https://github.com/alexgkendall/OPTICS_Clustering. Options: minPoints = 50, epsilon = 0.02. On the calculated reachability distance, we apply the *findpeaks* built-in Matlab function (using default parameters) to find the N most prominent peaks, where N represents the number of clusters.
- **GMM**: Matlab internal function
- **GDL**: Graph Agglomerative Clustering (GAC) toolbox. Authos: Wayne Zhang. <https://ch.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/38018-graph-agglomerative-clustering-gac-toolbox>
- **GAL**: Graph Agglomerative Clustering (GAC) toolbox. Authos: Wayne Zhang. <https://ch.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/38018-graph-agglomerative-clustering-gac-toolbox>

For all algorithms, the default parameters have been employed, unless otherwise specified.

Supplementary Method 4 : Cluster validation indices

To estimate the optimum number of clusters in the unlabeled data (MCBJ, IV and Raman), we used various internal cluster validation indices. A list of the internal CVIs can be found below.

The CVIs have been grouped by package and/or toolbox they belong to. Note that for several indices, several different implementations have been used.

- Built-in Matlab 2019b functions

Silhouette, Davies–Bouldin

- Cluster Validity Analysis Platform (CVAP) for Matlab by Kaijun Wang. Available at <https://ch.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/14620-cvap-cluster-validity-analysis-platform-cluster-analysis-and-validation-tool>.

Dunn, Krzanowski-Lai, Homogeneity, Separation, Weighted inter-intra.

- Publication: Joonas Hämäläinen et al.⁸, Algorithms, 10, p105 (2017). The Matlab scripts were kindly provided by the authors.

kCE, WB, Calinski–Harabasz, Pakhira-Bandyopadhyay-Maulik, Ray–Turi, Wemmert–Ganęski.

- NbClust⁹ package for R: Krzanowski-Lai, CCC, Hartigan, Scott, Marriot, TrCovW, TraceW, Friedman, Rubin, C-index, Duda, Pseudot2, Beale, Ratkowsky, Ball, Ptbiserial, Frey, McClain, Dunn, SD-index, SDbw.

Supplementary Note 1 : $M \times M$ feature space dependence

We have performed an additional benchmark on the 900 synthetic MCBJ datasets in which we vary the size of the $M \times M$ matrix between 2×2 and 100×100 using t-SNE and UMAP for dimensionality reduction to 3 dimensions, and GAL and J&W for clustering. The four resulting Fowlkes-Mallows index curves are shown below. We find that for all curves a steep increase in the FM-index is observed for $M < 10$ and a flattening out at $M \sim 20$. Interestingly, t-SNE seems to perform better than UMAP for higher dimensional reduction, with only a slight performance decrease for increasing M . For UMAP, a more steep decrease is observed for $M > 50$. Moreover, we find that for both cases GAL performs better than J&W. Finally, the plots also show the computational cost of both algorithms versus the number of bins. Both algorithms have a minimal cost around $M \sim 10$, with the cost monotonically increasing with increasing M . For t-SNE, the cost scales close to linear with M , while for UMAP an S-shaped curve is observed. Besides, UMAP

Supplementary Figure 3. **Influence of $M \times M$ on algorithm performance** Both the Fowlkes-Mallows index and the execution speed are shown.

is roughly 10x faster than t-SNE. Overall, our choice of 28×28 , inspired by the MNIST dataset, appears to be very well suited, balancing accuracy and computational cost.

Supplementary Note 2: Influence of dimensionality reduction

Supplementary Figure 4. Influence of dimensionality reduction on $28 \times 28 + t\text{-SNE}(\cos.)$ feature space for the GK, GMM, OPTICS, GAL and J&W algorithms on the FM index.

Supplementary Figure 4 shows the FM index obtained using the $28 \times 28 + t\text{-SNE}(\cos.)$ feature space for the GK, GMM, OPTICS, GAL and J&W algorithms. Only marginal improvements are

obtained by reducing the 784 dimensional feature to 7 dimensions instead of 3.

Supplementary Note 3 : Execution speeds

Supplementary Figure 5. Overview of the average execution speed obtained on the 900 simulated datasets of 2000 traces.

Supplementary Figure 5 presents the average computational cost of the various feature space methods and clustering algorithms as obtained on the 900 simulated datasets of 2000 traces each. The benchmarks were performed on a workstation with a AMD Ryzen thread Ripper 2990WX CPU (3.0 GHz, 32 cores) and 128 GB of RAM (DDR4, 2933 MHz). All timings assume the data to be loaded in the RAM. The table shows that significant difference exist. Dimensionality reduction using SNE, AE and Sammon mapping is expensive and exceeds several hundreds of seconds. t-SNE takes on average about 50 seconds to execute, while UMAP is almost an order

of magnitude faster. Altogether, UMAP is fast and accurate, and therefore our favorite approach. When comparing clustering algorithms, most of them only take several seconds to execute, with as negative outlier k-medoids.

Supplementary Note 4 : Additional datasets

One additional dataset was generated and benchmarked to account for additional (homoscedastic) noise. Two additional datasets were generated and benchmarked to account for heteroscedastic noise, scaling either with conductance or with electrode displacement. For the generation, the same original traces as in Figure 2 of the main text have been used. The details of the data generation are listed below:

Dataset main text: log10 distributed Gaussian noise (mean 0, std: 1/3 order of magnitude).

Dataset main text equal size: same as in main text, but with an equal number of traces in each class.

Dataset added noise: log10 distributed Gaussian noise (mean 0, std: 1 order of magnitude).

Dataset heteroscedasticity 1: log10 distributed Gaussian noise (mean 0, std: 1/3 order of magnitude) multiplied by twice the displacement in nanometers.

Dataset heteroscedasticity 2: log10 distributed Gaussian noise (mean 0, std: 1/3 order of magnitude) multiplied by $|\log_{10}(G/G_0)| / 3$.

An example dataset (109) for the three different noise types, as well as for equal-sized classes, is shown in Sup. Fig. 6, Sup. Fig. 7, Sup. Fig. 8, and Sup. Fig. 9. The corresponding Fowlkes-Mallows indices are shown in Sup. Fig. 10, Sup. Fig. 11, Sup. Fig. 12, and Sup. Fig. 13.

Supplementary Figure 6. 2D conductance-displacement histogram of generated clusters for dataset with added noise.

Supplementary Figure 7. 2D conductance-displacement histogram of generated clusters for dataset with heteroscedastic noise scaling with electrode separation.

Supplementary Figure 8. 2D conductance-displacement histogram of generated clusters for dataset with heteroscedastic noise scaling with conductance.

Supplementary Figure 9. 2D conductance-displacement histogram of generated clusters for dataset with equal-sized classes.

Supplementary Figure 10. Fowlkes-Mallows indices for dataset with added noise.

Supplementary Figure 11. Fowlkes-Mallows indices for dataset with heteroscedastic noise scaling with electrode separation.

Supplementary Figure 12. Fowlkes-Mallows indices for dataset with heteroscedastic noise scaling with conductance.

Supplementary Figure 13. Fowlkes-Mallows indices for dataset with equal-sized classes.

Supplementary Note 5 : CVI validation including badly performing feature space and clustering algorithm combinations

Supplementary Figure 14. Histogram of optimal number of clusters as predicted by the CVI for different combinations of feature space and clustering algorithms.

We performed an additional CVI analysis for the data presented in Figure 3 of the main text, but now including two of the worse performing feature spaces, namely raw + t-SNE (cos.) and raw + UMAP (cos.). The analysis shows that the combination of 28x28 + UMAP, GAL and 5 clusters again comes out as optimal.

Supplementary Note 6 : MCBJ additional clustering

Supplementary Figure 15. Clustered MCBJ data from Fig. 3 of the main text using 3 clusters.

Supplementary Figure 16. Clustered MCBJ data from Fig. 3 of the main text using 4 clusters.

Supplementary Figure 17. Clustered MCBJ data from Fig. 3 of the main text using 5 clusters.

Supplementary Figure 18. Clustered MCBJ data from Fig. 3 of the main text using 6 clusters.

Supplementary Figure 19. Clustered MCBJ data from Fig. 3 of the main text using 7 clusters.

Supplementary Note 7 : Benchmark Raman dataset

We generated a dataset for benchmarking of Raman spectra. As for the MCBJ datasets, random spectra were selected from the experimental dataset shown in Figure 5 of the main text. Gaussian noise (mean 0, std 15 counts) was added to each trace. Moreover, a normal distributed shift (mean 0, std 20) was added to the Raman shift axis. An example dataset can be found in Supplementary Figure 20. The resulting Fowlkes-Mallows indices are shown in Supplementary Figure 21

Supplementary Figure 20. Example dataset of generated Raman spectra.

Supplementary Figure 21. Fowlkes-Mallows indices for Raman dataset.

Supplementary Note 8 : Raman Spectroscopy

The silicon nitride frame was fabricated as described by Celebi *et al.*¹⁰. A Ti/Au (5/40nm) layer was deposited on top of the frame using an electron beam evaporator. The graphene was grown and transfer onto the frame by Applied Nanolayers (ANL), Delft, The Netherlands. For the irradiation of the freestanding graphene membrane we used a He-ion microscope (Zeiss Orion), equipped with a Raith Elphy MultiBeam pattern generator. The microscope was operated at 30 keV using a probe current of 5.5 pA at a chamber pressure of $7 \cdot 10^5$ Pa. The ion dose was controlled by the exposure dwell time of each pixel ranging from 0.3 ms to 1.5 ms. The quadrants, counted in clockwise direction starting from the upper left one, have been exposed to 0, 1, 2.5, $5 \cdot 10^{18}$ He⁺/m² referred as low, medium and high respectively.

Supplementary Figure 22. Histogram of predicted number of cluster using the CVI's for the 28×28 + UMAP(cos.) feature space and GAL clustering algorithm.

Supplementary Figure 22 shows the CVI analysis performed for the Raman data on the 28×28 + UMAP(cos.) feature space and GAL clustering algorithm, pointing to an optimum number of clusters of 7.

Supplementary references

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- ¹ Frisenda, R., Stefani, D. & van der Zant, H. S. J. Quantum Transport through a Single Conjugated Rigid Molecule, a Mechanical Break Junction Study. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **51**, 1359–1367 (2018).
 - ² Lemmer, M., Inkpen, M. S., Kornysheva, K., Long, N. J. & Albrecht, T. Unsupervised vector-based classification of single-molecule charge transport data. *Nature Communications* **7** (2016).
 - ³ Huang, F. *et al.* Automatic classification of single-molecule charge transport data with an unsupervised machine-learning algorithm. *Physical Chemistry Chemical Physics* (2019).
 - ⁴ Cabosart, D. *et al.* A reference-free clustering method for the analysis of molecular break-junction measurements. *Applied Physics Letters* **114** (2019).

- ⁵ Van Der Maaten, L., Postma, E. & Van den Herik, J. Dimensionality reduction: a comparative review. *J Mach Learn Res* **10**, 66–71 (2009).
- ⁶ Van Der Maaten, L. & Hinton, G. Visualizing Data using t-SNE. *Journal of Machine Learning Research* **9**, 2579–2605 (2008).
- ⁷ McInnes, L., Healy, J., Saul, N. & Großberger, L. UMAP: Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection. *Journal of Open Source Software* **3**, 861 (2018).
- ⁸ Hämäläinen, J., Jauhiainen, S. & Kärkkäinen, T. Comparison of Internal Clustering Validation Indices for Prototype-Based Clustering. *Algorithms* **10**, 105 (2017).
- ⁹ Charrad, M., Ghazzali, N., Boiteau, V. & Niknafs, A. Nbclust: An r package for determining the relevant number of clusters in a data set. *Journal of Statistical Software, Articles* **61**, 1–36 (2014).
- ¹⁰ Celebi, K. *et al.* Ultimate permeation across atomically thin porous graphene. *Science* **344**, 289–292 (2014).